

The Effect of Fisheries Product Processing and Marketing Programs on the Empowerment of Coastal Women in North Maluku Province, Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 13, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: August 29, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Coastal Women, Empowerment, Fisheries Product Processing</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5332485</p>	<p><i>This article describes about the impact of fisheries product processing program on coastal women in North Maluku. 90% of women are involved in fisheries business of small scale industries. This is very helpful in empowering women economically to fulfill family necessary but it is still questionable whether it will make women successful in making women empowered in the family. Impact analysis of fisheries business development program can be seen from several dimensions, namely from 1) consumption pattern 2) quality of access and control 3) Decision Making 4) Self-esteem of wife. The method used in this research was quantitative method with multivariate measurement analysis. Questionnaires were distributed to women targeted by the fisheries product processing program. The theory used in the analysis was the theory of Longwee women's empowerment. The results found that the Fisheries Product Processing Program has positive influence. The more the women could access the program, the higher their power made important decision in life.</i></p>

Introduction

North Maluku is a strategic area for island or coastal-based economic development. The location of the archipelago with a group of islands produces abundant marine resources. The food processing program is one of the government's interventions to open up employment opportunities and for the welfare of coastal community in the small island. The participation of coastal women reaches 90% in the fishery product business consisting of smoked fish, shredded fish, fish sauce, fish meatball, seaweed syrup and fish stick. This article will describe how significance the influence of the program to women's activities in the family in term of women's power in decision making, access and control of important rules in the family.

Most of research on women's empowerment has still focused on economy improvement and the eradication of violence experienced by women in the household (Harper, 2013; Santos, 2015; Nawaz, 2018; Gutierrez, et al, 2019). But this research illustrates that the problem of coastal women is not only about economic prosperity, but also on the social side of the family as seen from the power of women in controlling self-interest in the family, as well as a fair decision-making process in the family. The context of developing country such as Indonesia, the program that was created is still focused on economic improvement, but not included the social and cultural factors of the community in empowerment program and coastal community development. So many government programs fails because the intervention process only looks at economic problems, whereas the social and cultural problems of Indonesia's multicultural society are far more important to be addressed than economic alleviation. The different cultural characteristics among community have an impact on their response to government program. Thus Indonesian government needs empowerment programs that are oriented towards economic, social and cultural improvement and are just for the lives of women and coastal families.

This research is important for the sustainability of coastal community, especially women. The urgency of this research is also important, namely to know the effect of government programs aimed at improving the economy toward the quality of women's social lives. The most important thing in this research is the social welfare of coastal women. The state has intervened in various programs without consider the social aspects of women who play an important role in the families of coastal community who live in poverty. The dilemma position of coastal women carries out their duties with two tasks, namely as a wife who helps husband earn money and also serves as a mother in caring for children. The government must intervene and help to alleviate the burden of coastal women by organizing empowerment programs for coastal women and the economic development for fishing community, as well as social and cultural development so the creation of fishing community is economically and socially prosperous based on their culture.

WOMEN COASTAL AND FISHERIES RESULT

One of the government's programs to empower coastal community is to provide development activity related to fishery product. Coastal women play an extraordinary role in this program. All program target groups are

women who receive guidance and assistance in being able to process fishery product into economic value product. The aim is to improve the standard of living of family in coastal area. This program has been running from 2012 until now. The form of activities of this program are 1) Management Assistance for Fisheries Product Processing and Marketing Group, 2) Aid with Equipment and Infrastructure of Processed Fish Product Packaging, 3) Aid for Cold Chain Facility for Fish Storage 3) Obtaining Halal Certificate for the Product. In essence, these programs and activities aim to empower the fishermen's wives to help them fulfill the economic necessary of fishermen families to face of famine or economic crisis.

The target of this program is all coastal communities who want to develop fisheries businesses but in the reality, this program just involved women. In the context of the central government namely the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries of the Republic of Indonesia, this fisheries business program is one of the government's policies to empower women fishermen or fishermen's wives to achieve the economic prosperity of coastal community but awareness of the importance of the coastal women role in the implementation of programs at the Provincial and District level has not been conveyed properly. So the government does not yet understand that the processed fishery program is intended to empower women in the coastal area.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In the social and economic life of coastal community, women play an important role in helping their husband as fishermen. Coastal women play a role in sustaining the economy of poor families in coastal areas (Mulyadi, 2012; Kuncoro, 2015; Islamiyah, 2016; Ramachandran, 2017; Shakir, 2017). Seeing the important role of coastal women, this research is important to be carried out and published to be a reference for improving government programs to empower coastal women not only in economic aspect but also in social aspect. Because of the role of women in the family is quite large, namely as a mother for children and also as a wife who is devoted to her husband. Sarah Longwee (1991) outlines the theory of women's empowerment in government programs or policies that approach women's activities. Some aspects seen are 1) Women's welfare related to nutritional consumption in the family, 2) Access and control related to women's power over economic access in the family, 3) Constantialization is women's awareness of the equitable distribution of sexual work, this can be seen from the quality of women decision making in the family, 4) Women's participation in the process of decision making and policy making start from problem identification to the program evaluation stage, 5) The function of controlling women as wives in household rules. In the context of this research, the theory is used to see the influence of the program on the lives of women in the family. The longwee five indicators of women's empowerment are reduced to indicators like the table below:

Table 1
Dissemination of Indicator for Women's Empowerment

Indicator	Statement
1. Consumption Pattern	- I eat 3 times a day
	- My family eats 3 times a day
2. Access and Control	- I use my salary for personal need
	- I use my saving for personal need
	- I ask my husband for money to fulfill household need
	- I ask my husband for money to fulfill my need
	- When we are in economic crisis, my husband is looking for additional work
3. Decision Making	- I decide on the family food menu
	- I decide to buy household equipment
	- I manage our child's school payment
	- I decide the education of our son / daughter
	- I decide the choice of contraception
	- I decide the fish catch processing

	- I can travel outside of the house without my husband's permission
	- I can borrow money for family / household need
	- I can take care the health of our son / daughter.
	- I am the one who determines the marketing of processed fish product
	- I can sit on public position
4. Self-Esteem	- I am punished if I am suspected of being unfaithful
	- I am punished for showing disrespect to my mother or father in-law
	- I am punished if I left my house without my husband's permission
	- I am punished for neglecting children and house work
	- I am punished for not cooking food for family properly

METHODOLOGY

Respondents from this research were 50 women who were the beneficiaries of the fisheries product processing and marketing program in three regions in North Maluku, namely Ternate City, Halmahera Selatan Regency and Morotai Island. The method used in this study was quantitative method by using Likert scale measurement scale with Likert scale, the variables to be measured are explained into indicator variables. Then the indicator is used as the starting point for compiling instrument items in the form of statements and given the later scale that matched the statement namely score 4 for Always, score 3 for often, score 2 for sometimes and score 1 for never. To conduct data analysis and answer questions about the influence of processing and marketing programs of fisheries result, this research used Multivariate analysis through SPSS. Multivariate consists of independent / constant variable and dependent variable. The following is an overview of multivariate measurement.

Figure 1: Dependent and Independent Variable Relationship Chart

Figure 1 above consisted of the dependent variable namely women's empowerment as measured by consumption pattern, access, decision making and self-esteem. Then the constant variable was program services that consisted of a series of fishery product processing and marketing program activities. Therefore, the question proposed is how significance the influence of the program services obtained by women on consumption pattern, access, decision making and women's self-esteem in the household.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The multivariate analysis used in this study aimed to determine the effect of fisheries product processing programs on the women or wives empowerment in the household. The results of the univariate analysis are presented as follows:

1. The Effect of Fisheries Product Processing Program Against Women's Consumption Pattern in Household

Table 2
The Result of the Effect of Fisheries Product Processing on Women's Consumption Pattern in Household Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5,379	,406		13,259	,000
	Program Service Aspect	,462	,182	,344	2,537	,014

a. Dependent Variable: Consumption Pattern

Source : Data processed 2019

Based on Table 2 above, it is known that t-value was **2,537** with significance value was **0,014**. t-value indicated positive value, which means that the service aspect of the fishery product processing program has positive influence on the consumption pattern of women in the household, which means that the better the service aspect of the fishery product processing program, the better the consumption pattern of women in the household. Then the significance value indicated smaller value than $\alpha = 0,05$ ($0,014 < 0,05$) which means that the service aspect of fishery product processing program has significant effect on women's consumption pattern in the household.

2. The Effect of Fisheries Product Processing Program on Women's Access and Control in the Household

Table 3
The Result of the Effect of Fisheries Product Processing on Women's Access and Control in the Household Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	10,247	1,293		7,926	,000
	Program Service Aspect	1,025	,581	,247	1,766	,084

a. Dependent Variable: Access and Control

Source: Data processed 2019

Based on Table 3 above, it is known that t-value was **1,766** with significance value was **0,084**. The t-value value showed positive value which means that the service aspect of fishery product processing program has positive influence on women's access and control in the household, which means that the better the service aspect of the fishery product processing program, the better the access and control of women in the household. Then the significance value indicated greater value than $\alpha = 0,05$ ($0,084 > 0,05$) which means that the service aspect of the fishery product processing program has no significant effect on women's access and control in the household.

3. The Effect of Fisheries Product Processing Program on Women's Decision Making in the Household

Table 4

The Result of the Effect of Fisheries Product Processing on Women's Decision Making in the Household Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	24,343	2,110		11,535	,000
	Program Service Aspect	2,441	,948	,348	2,576	,013

a. Dependent Variable: Decision-making

Source : Data processed 2019

Based on Table 4 above, it is known that t-test value was **2,576** with significance value was **0,013**. The t-value showed positive value which means that the service aspect of fishery product processing program has positive influence on women's decision making in the household, which means that the better the service aspect of the fishery product processing program, the better the women's decision making in the household. Then the significance value indicated smaller value than $\alpha = 0,05$ ($0,013 < 0,05$) which means that the service aspect of the fishery product processing program has significant effect on women's decision making in the household.

4. The Effect of Fisheries Product Processing Programs on Women's Self-Esteem in the Household

Table 5
The Effect of Fisheries Product Processing on Women's Self-Esteem in the Household Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	18,540	1,178		15,741	,000
	Program Service Aspect	,096	,529	,026	,181	,857

a. Dependent Variable: Self Esteem

Source : Data processed 2019

Based on Table 5 above, it is known that the t-value was **0,181** with significance value was **0,857**. The value of t-count showed positive value which means that the service aspect of fishery product processing program has positive influence on women's self-esteem in the household, which means that the better the service aspect of the fishery product processing program, the better the self-esteem of women in the household. Then the significance value indicated greater value than $\alpha = 0,05$ ($0,857 > 0,05$) which means that the service aspect of the fishery product processing program has no significant effect on women's self-esteem in the household.

5. The Effect of Fisheries Product Processing Program on Overall Indicators of Women's Empowerment in the Household

Table 6
The Result of the Effect of Fisheries Product Processing on Overall Indicators of Women's Empowerment in the Household Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	58,510	2,554		22,906	,000
	Program Service Aspect	4,024	1,147	,452	3,509	,001

a. Dependent Variable: Empowerment

Source: Proceed data 2019

Based on Table 6 above, it is known that t-test value was **3,509** with significance value was **0,001**. The t-value indicated positive value, which means that the service aspect of fishery product processing

program has positive influence on all indicators of women's empowerment in the household, which means that the better the service aspect of the fishery product processing program, the better all indicators of women's empowerment in the household. Then the significance value indicated smaller value than $\alpha = 0,05$ ($0,001 < 0,05$) which means that the service aspect of the fishery product processing program has significant effect on all indicators of women's empowerment in the household.

CONCLUSION

The result of the study explained that the processing and marketing of fishery product program that aimed to improve the family economy in coastal area in order bring positive impact on the empowerment quality of coastal women who act as wife in the household. Most of research on women's empowerment has focused on improving the economy with a variety of financial aid or research on women's domestic violence. The novelty of this research was the existence of economic welfare improvement program that has positive impact on the women social aspect in the family. Thus Sarah Longwe's analysis of the quality of the program was used because the beneficiaries were women, this service was in neutral position which means that the program has positive impact on women's social quality even though the program has not included detailed coastal women's issues in the institutional regulatory framework.

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